

DIGITAL INCLUSION STRATEGIES AND YOUTH SOCIO-ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT: EVIDENCE FROM AREKA, WOLAITA ZONE, ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between digital inclusion strategies and youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. The objectives were to: (i) assess youth access to digital technologies and infrastructure, (ii) evaluate the impact of digital literacy programs, (iii) analyze the role of government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in promoting digital inclusion, and (iv) identify strategies to enhance youth empowerment through digital means. A convergent mixed-methods design was adopted, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to 292 youth aged 18–34 years, selected via stratified random sampling. Qualitative data were gathered through 50 semi-structured interviews and five focus group discussions (50 participants in total), purposively selected to provide deeper insights. The study was anchored in the Digital Divide Theory, Empowerment Theory, Technology Acceptance Model, and Social Capital Theory. The findings revealed that while smartphone access was relatively high (mean = 3.31), access to laptops (mean = 2.25) and tablets (mean = 1.93) remained low. Internet connectivity scored a moderate mean of 2.96, with most youth relying on costly mobile data. Participation in digital literacy programs was limited (mean = 2.44), with most youth acquiring only basic computer skills (mean = 2.90), while advanced skills such as coding (mean = 2.29) and cybersecurity (mean = 2.03) were rarely attained. Although digital tools improved educational opportunities and employability, youth engagement in digital entrepreneurship remained low. Barriers identified included high costs of devices and internet, weak digital infrastructure, and socio-cultural constraints, particularly gender disparities affecting young women. The study concluded that digital inclusion contributes positively to youth socio-economic empowerment but is hindered by affordability, infrastructural gaps, and limited access to advanced digital skills. It is recommended that policymakers and development partners: (i) expand digital literacy programs to include advanced skills such as coding and cybersecurity, (ii) subsidize devices and internet costs to improve affordability, (iii) invest in broadband infrastructure for rural and semi-urban areas, and (iv) strengthen government–NGO partnerships to promote sustainable and inclusive digital entrepreneurship initiatives. Future research should focus on long-term impacts of digital inclusion and explore gender-specific barriers affecting rural youth.

Keywords : - Digital technologies, Digital access, Socio-economic empowerment, Digital inclusion strategies, Digital infrastructure, Digital technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Globally, initiatives aimed at promoting digital inclusion have gained significant traction in the last decade. The World Economic Forum's EDISON Alliance seeks to connect over one billion people to digital services by 2025, focusing on key areas such as healthcare, education, and finance. These areas are essential for youth empowerment, providing opportunities to access information and services that can improve their quality of life. Governments and non-governmental organizations have increasingly acknowledged that digital access is a key enabler of

social mobility, with digital platforms offering young people opportunities to develop skills, seek employment, and engage in business ventures. As such, the international community has made digital inclusion a priority to ensure that young people, particularly in underserved regions, can fully participate in the global digital economy (World Economic Forum, 2021). Despite these efforts, challenges persist, particularly in providing affordable internet access and addressing the digital literacy gap, which continues to hinder youth from leveraging digital technologies to their advantage.

Recent reports have highlighted that approximately 2.6 billion people worldwide still lack access to the internet, with a disproportionate number of these individuals being youth in developing countries (International Telecommunication Union, 2021). These statistics underscore the need for a focused effort to improve both access and digital literacy, particularly in regions where technological infrastructure is underdeveloped. Governments and private sectors are encouraged to collaborate on initiatives that ensure affordable connectivity, training programs, and accessible technology for youth. The Digital Cooperation Organization has pointed out that overcoming the digital divide is vital for reducing economic inequalities and enhancing the socio-political participation of youth worldwide (DCO, 2022). Ensuring equal access to digital resources will enable youth to not only gain employment but also engage in entrepreneurship, contributing to sustainable economic development. Thus, global digital inclusion efforts remain an essential component of youth empowerment strategies, aiming to level the playing field for all young people, regardless of their socio-economic background.

Regional disparities within Ethiopia exacerbate the challenges faced by the youth in Areka, especially when compared to urban areas such as Addis Ababa, Hawassa, Adama, and Bahir Dar. Rural areas like Areka have less robust internet infrastructure, which significantly impacts the ability of youth to access online educational platforms or seek digital employment opportunities. Despite these challenges, there is a growing recognition that improving digital literacy and infrastructure in areas like Areka is vital for the socio-economic development of youth. The government's ongoing efforts to improve digital access across the country, such as the Digital Ethiopia 2025 initiative, aim to tackle some of these gaps by promoting digital literacy programs and improving digital infrastructure (Ministry of Innovation and Technology, 2021). There are regional efforts to foster collaboration between educational institutions, the private sector, and government agencies to create a more inclusive digital ecosystem. Such collaborations are critical for ensuring that the youth in Areka can take full advantage of the opportunities offered by the digital economy. To achieve this, both local and

national efforts need to align to overcome existing barriers and empower youth to participate in the digital age (World Bank, 2020).

While the national strategy sets ambitious goals, the regional implementation of digital inclusion policies has faced several challenges, particularly in rural and underserved areas. The disparities in infrastructure, coupled with limited access to affordable technology, have hindered many youth from participating in digital economies. The African Union's Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020–2030) aims to tackle these disparities by improving digital connectivity across the continent, with a focus on youth development and digital skills training (African Union, 2020). In Ethiopia, this has translated into efforts to improve internet access, provide low-cost digital devices, and develop training programs to boost digital literacy. However, even with these initiatives, progress has been uneven, and there remains a significant gap between urban and rural youth in terms of digital access and literacy. For youth in rural areas, these barriers to digital access further reinforce existing socio-economic disparities, limiting their opportunities to improve their livelihoods through digital means (World Bank, 2021).

Efforts to address these disparities have been met with mixed results, with some regional programs focusing on providing mobile and internet access in underserved communities, while others have concentrated on equipping young people with digital skills for employment and entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, the digital divide remains a persistent issue, and continued regional collaboration is essential for ensuring that all youth, regardless of location, have access to the benefits of the digital economy. Ethiopia's youth are seen as key drivers of socio-economic change, and regional strategies that prioritize digital literacy and access to technology are vital in fostering their empowerment. With the right infrastructure, policy support, and targeted training, digital inclusion can provide the tools necessary for Ethiopia's youth to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world (UNESCO, 2021).

While regional initiatives in Ethiopia and Sub-Saharan Africa show promise, achieving full digital inclusion for youth requires overcoming significant barriers. Access to digital technologies, affordable internet, and

digital literacy programs must be prioritized in order to bridge the gap and unlock the full potential of youth in the digital economy. This regional approach, if fully realized, will contribute significantly to the empowerment of young people, providing them with the tools to improve their socio-economic conditions and contribute to national development.

Areka, located in the Wolaita Zone of Southern Ethiopia, exemplifies the challenges faced by rural areas in integrating youth into the digital economy. Despite its administrative significance and growing population, Areka struggles with limited access to digital infrastructure, which hampers the ability of its youth to engage in technological advancements. The town's youth, a significant portion of its population, face limited opportunities for economic and social mobility due to inadequate access to digital tools and the internet. According to recent reports, the majority of youth in Areka lack the necessary skills and resources to effectively participate in the digital economy, leaving them with fewer employment opportunities and a lack of entrepreneurial prospects (World Bank, 2021). Local youth initiatives, such as those by the Ministry of Education and NGOs, have been implemented to address these barriers by offering digital literacy training and entrepreneurship support programs. These programs aim to equip young people with critical digital skills that will allow them to compete in an increasingly technology-driven job market. Despite these efforts, challenges such as the high cost of digital devices, unreliable internet access, and insufficient awareness about the potential of digital technologies continue to limit the effectiveness of these programs (UNDP, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, digital inclusion has become a crucial factor in the socio-economic development of youth globally, particularly in empowering them to navigate and thrive in the digital world. Digital technologies, including access to the internet and digital literacy programs, provide young people with essential tools for improving their education, securing employment, and starting entrepreneurial ventures. Despite these potential benefits, significant challenges remain in ensuring equal access to such resources, especially in developing countries like Ethiopia. In Ethiopia, youth face persistent barriers to digital inclusion, including

inadequate infrastructure, unreliable internet connectivity, and limited access to digital skills training. These constraints prevent them from fully participating in the digital economy, thereby exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities (Howard, 2023). The national literacy rate remains below 60%, while digital literacy is even lower, at only 9.9% according to the Global Digital Skills Index (2021). This digital skill gap severely hinders youth from benefiting from the transformative potential of technology for personal and professional development (Upadhyaya et al., 2019). Without access to essential digital tools and training, Ethiopian youth particularly those in rural areas struggle to access education, seek employment, or engage in entrepreneurial activities, leaving them further disadvantaged in a rapidly digitizing world (Costantinos, 2020). Moreover, with over 80% of Ethiopia's population lacking internet access, the majority of youth remain excluded from opportunities in the global digital economy (Costantinos, 2020).

The lack of digital inclusion restricts youth opportunities for socio-economic mobility, perpetuates unemployment, and widens economic disparities. Existing studies in Ethiopia have primarily focused on internet access and higher education, but they often overlook the unique needs of rural and low-income youth. These studies fail to address the broader dimensions of digital literacy and its impact on empowerment (ILO, 2022; Beyene et al., 2022).

If this problem persists, Ethiopian youth particularly those in underserved areas like Areka will continue to face marginalization, limited access to education, chronic unemployment, and exclusion from entrepreneurial opportunities. This will not only deepen socio-economic inequalities but also hinder the country's progress toward national development goals and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Therefore, this study investigates the relationship between digital inclusion strategies and the socio-economic empowerment of youth in Areka town. It explores how digital inclusion can create new opportunities in education, employment, and social engagement, ultimately contributing to the reduction of socio-economic inequalities in the region.

Justification of the Study

This study is significant as it addresses a critical gap in the existing literature by investigating the intersection of digital inclusion strategies and youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. While both digital inclusion and youth empowerment have been widely recognized as essential for fostering sustainable development, limited research has specifically explored how these two factors interact within the context of rural and underserved areas like Wolaita Zone (Alemneh & Mamo, 2022). Existing studies have largely focused on urban settings or general national-level analyses, which often overlook the unique socio-economic challenges and opportunities faced by youth in rural areas. This gap in the literature left an incomplete understanding of how digital inclusion could directly influence socio-economic development among youth in rural Ethiopia. As such, this research aimed to fill this void by providing critical insights into the barriers and enablers of youth empowerment through digital means within the specific socio-economic context of Areka.

The findings from this study are expected to provide valuable contributions to the field, particularly for policymakers, development practitioners, civil society organizations, and other stakeholders involved in youth development and digital transformation efforts. By closely analyzing the relationship between digital inclusion and youth socio-economic empowerment, the study offers empirical evidence that can inform policy formulation and the design of programmatic interventions tailored to the specific needs of youth in Areka. The results offer evidence-based strategies that can guide the implementation of effective policies and digital inclusion programs, which, in turn, can better empower youth by improving access to digital tools, enhancing their skills, and creating new opportunities for employment and entrepreneurship (World Bank, 2021).

This research contributes to the broader theoretical understanding of how digital inclusion can serve as a catalyst for youth empowerment. It provides practical interventions and insights on how digital tools and platforms can be better integrated into the socio-economic development efforts in underserved areas. By linking theoretical frameworks to the real-world

challenges faced by youth, the study enhances knowledge on the intersection of technology, education, and economic growth for rural youth (Schwab, 2020). It also provides a comprehensive understanding of how digital technologies can bridge gaps in education, employment, and social engagement, ultimately leading to greater empowerment for youth in areas that have traditionally been marginalized.

In addition to advancing theoretical perspectives, this study offers actionable recommendations for designing digital inclusion strategies that promote socio-economic empowerment. These recommendations are grounded in empirical data collected from the study area, ensuring they are contextually relevant and adaptable to the specific socio-economic dynamics of Wolaita Zone. Based on the study's findings, targeted interventions are suggested that can improve access to digital resources, enhance digital literacy, and foster entrepreneurial opportunities. The study emphasizes that increasing access to affordable digital devices, improving internet connectivity, and expanding digital skills training are essential to enhancing the employability and entrepreneurial potential of youth in Areka.

The research underscores the importance of creating policies and programs that are inclusive and tailored to the specific needs of the youth population in the region. Many youth, particularly those from low-income households or rural areas, face significant barriers to accessing digital resources. These include high costs, unreliable internet connections, and a lack of awareness about available digital platforms and educational tools. By addressing these barriers, the recommendations aim to provide youth with the digital tools they need to succeed in the global economy. This research thus contributes to the development of digital inclusion initiatives that can directly enhance the lives of youth in Areka, helping them realize their potential through improved access to digital education and entrepreneurial opportunities (Bennett et al., 2021).

One of the significant contributions of this study is that it bridges the gap between theory and practice in the field of digital inclusion and youth empowerment. By focusing on the local context of Areka, the study provides tailored recommendations that are both actionable and relevant to the specific needs of youth

in the region. The findings not only deepen the understanding of the challenges faced by youth in rural Ethiopia but also offer solutions that could have broader implications for digital inclusion initiatives in other parts of Ethiopia and Sub-Saharan Africa. The study ultimately justifies its importance by contributing new knowledge to the field, informing policy on youth empowerment and digital inclusion, and supporting sustainable socio-economic development in Areka.

This research enhances understanding of how digital inclusion can empower youth and improve their socio-economic conditions, particularly in areas that are typically underserved or excluded from digital development. By promoting digital skills, entrepreneurship, and increased access to resources, digital inclusion strategies have the potential to

significantly reduce socio-economic disparities and foster more inclusive growth in rural areas (ILO, 2022).

This study not only contributes to the academic discourse on digital inclusion but also serves as a practical tool for policymakers and development practitioners working in the digital transformation space. Its findings can guide future efforts aimed at improving the digital empowerment of youth in rural Ethiopia and similar regions, helping to create a more equitable digital ecosystem that supports youth in reaching their full potential. By bridging the gap between theory and practice, the study presents a comprehensive framework for understanding and implementing digital inclusion strategies that have the power to transform youth’s socio-economic conditions and contribute to long-term development goals.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Divide Theory

The Digital Divide Theory (DDT) was introduced by Pippa Norris in 2001 in her seminal work *Digital Divide: Civic Engagement, Information Poverty, and the Internet Worldwide*. Norris's research focused on the disparities in access to digital technologies across different countries, highlighting the widening gap between those who have access to the internet and digital tools and those who do not. Norris argued that unequal access to these technologies exacerbates existing social inequalities, thus hindering participation in the global economy and diminishing democratic engagement. This gap, often observed between developed and developing nations, places rural regions, such as the Wolaita Zone in Ethiopia, at a distinct disadvantage. Norris's early conceptualization of the digital divide was largely concerned with the disparity in access between countries, but this concept has since evolved to account for more granular differences within countries, regions, and communities. This development was extended by scholars such as van Dijk (2017), who further explored how these divides manifest not only in terms of access to technology but also in terms of skills, motivations, and usage.

This theory is highly relevant to the study of digital inclusion strategies in Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia, particularly in the context of youth socio-economic empowerment. The theory provides a useful lens through which to examine how digital inclusion can influence youth access to educational resources, employment opportunities, and social participation in the digital age. The youth in Areka, Wolaita Zone, often face significant challenges in accessing digital technologies and acquiring the necessary skills to use them effectively. These barriers are compounded by the socio-economic conditions prevalent in the region, where infrastructure is often underdeveloped, and educational systems may not adequately prepare youth for participation in a digitally connected world (World Bank, 2021). By applying the Digital Divide Theory, this study aims to assess how gaps in access, skills, and usage limit the socio-economic empowerment of youth in Areka and identify strategies for overcoming these barriers.

One of the major advantages of the Digital Divide Theory is its comprehensive framework for understanding the different factors contributing to digital inequality. By considering not only physical access to technology but also the skills and motivations required to use it, the theory allows for a nuanced analysis of the barriers to digital inclusion. This makes it particularly useful for studying regions like Wolaita Zone, where infrastructural issues, such as unreliable internet connectivity and limited access to digital devices, intersect with socio-cultural factors that may influence youth engagement with technology (UNDP, 2022). Furthermore, the theory's focus on usage patterns underscores the need to move beyond mere access and ensure that youth are equipped to use digital technologies in ways that contribute to their socio-economic development.

Despite its strengths, the Digital Divide Theory has limitations. One significant critique is that it may overly focus on individual-level factors while underplaying broader structural issues that contribute to digital exclusion. For example, in rural Ethiopia, gender disparities, cultural attitudes towards technology, and lack of community support can exacerbate the divide and hinder digital inclusion efforts. The theory also tends to assume that once access is provided, individuals will automatically gain the necessary skills and motivation to use digital technologies effectively. In reality, community-level support, targeted training programs, and policy interventions are often required to enable individuals to bridge the digital divide (Warschauer, 2003). The theory's focus on individual capabilities may overlook the need for systemic change in infrastructure, policies, and social norms that perpetuate digital exclusion.

The Digital Divide Theory provides a critical framework for understanding the challenges faced by youth in Areka, Wolaita Zone, in accessing and effectively using digital technologies. By considering access, skills, and usage as interconnected dimensions, the theory enables a deeper exploration of the barriers to digital inclusion and the potential solutions for overcoming these barriers. Despite its limitations, particularly in addressing broader socio-cultural factors, the theory remains a valuable tool for analyzing the complex relationship between digital inclusion and youth socio-economic empowerment.

This study aims to build upon the theory by examining how targeted digital inclusion strategies can reduce the digital divide and enhance youth socio-economic opportunities in rural Ethiopia.

Digital Inclusion and Youth Socio-Economic Empowerment

Alemneh and Mamo (2022) conducted a study titled *Digital Inclusion Strategies for Youth Empowerment in Ethiopia: Policy Perspectives and Challenges*. This qualitative study explored the role of digital inclusion strategies in empowering youth, focusing on rural Ethiopia. Using interviews and focus group discussions with policymakers, youth participants, and NGO representatives, the study examined the impact of digital literacy programs on youth socio-economic outcomes. The findings revealed that digital literacy programs were effective in improving employment prospects and enabling youth to participate in the digital economy. However, significant challenges, such as limited digital infrastructure and unreliable internet connectivity, hindered the full participation of youth in the digital economy. The study concluded that improving digital infrastructure, alongside digital literacy programs, is critical to achieving meaningful youth empowerment in Ethiopia (Alemneh & Mamo, 2022).

Bennett, Johnson, and Liu (2021) explored *The Impact of Digital Literacy on Youth Economic Participation in Developing Countries*. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining surveys with 500 youth participants and semi-structured interviews to explore the relationship between digital literacy and youth employment. The research found that digital literacy significantly improved youth participation in the digital economy, with increases in employment and entrepreneurial activity among digitally literate youth. Despite this, the study also highlighted challenges related to limited internet access in rural areas, which restricted the effectiveness of digital literacy programs. The authors concluded that both digital access and skills development are crucial in empowering youth economically and that government efforts should focus on improving infrastructure and expanding digital education opportunities (Bennett, Johnson, & Liu, 2021).

Elgar et al. (2024) examined *Social Participation, Empowerment, and Digital Inclusion in Youth Development*. This longitudinal study aimed to assess the long-term impact of digital inclusion programs on youth socio-economic participation. The study tracked youth participants over two years, collecting data through surveys and interviews. The findings indicated that digital skills fostered greater socio-political participation and increased opportunities for employment and entrepreneurship. The research also highlighted the importance of social capital, noting that youth with strong community ties were more likely to benefit from digital inclusion programs. The study concluded that integrating social capital with digital inclusion efforts could significantly enhance youth empowerment in rural communities (Elgar et al., 2024).

Freire (2020), in his work *Pedagogy of the Oppressed and Digital Literacy for Youth Empowerment*, proposed a conceptual framework for understanding youth empowerment through education, with a focus on digital literacy. This qualitative study applied Freire's pedagogical principles to analyze digital literacy programs in rural Brazil, emphasizing that digital literacy can empower marginalized youth by providing them with both technological competencies and the critical thinking skills needed to address social and economic inequalities. The findings suggested that digital tools can be effective in empowering youth if they are used to address real-world socio-economic issues, such as unemployment and poverty. The study concluded that digital literacy programs must be integrated into broader educational strategies that equip youth to challenge the socio-economic structures that oppress them (Freire, 2020).

The UNDP (2022) report *Digital Inclusion for Youth Empowerment: A Roadmap for Change in Africa* examined digital inclusion strategies across Sub-Saharan Africa, focusing on Ethiopia. The study used secondary data and expert interviews to explore how digital inclusion affects youth empowerment. The findings demonstrated that access to digital technologies significantly improved youth's employment prospects, especially in the informal sector, by providing access to remote work and entrepreneurial opportunities. The report also identified barriers to digital inclusion, including

limited digital infrastructure and low digital literacy in rural areas. The authors concluded that addressing both infrastructure challenges and digital skills gaps is essential for enhancing youth empowerment through digital inclusion (UNDP, 2022).

The World Bank (2021) report *The Role of Digital Technology in Youth Empowerment in Africa* analyzed the impact of digital technology on youth socio-economic development across East Africa. The study utilized a quantitative approach, analyzing data from over 1,000 youth participants. The results indicated that access to digital technologies had a positive effect on youth employment, particularly in rural areas, by providing new opportunities for job searching, online education, and entrepreneurship. The study also highlighted that a lack of internet connectivity and digital skills remained significant barriers for many youths. The World Bank concluded that comprehensive digital inclusion strategies, including both improved infrastructure and digital literacy programs, are necessary to ensure that youth can fully benefit from digital technologies (World Bank, 2021).

Van Dijk (2017) explored the *Impact of Access and Usage in Socio-Economic Development* through his study on the digital divide. This mixed-methods study examined the impact of digital exclusion on socio-economic development, particularly in rural Europe. The research found that the digital divide not only limited access to digital resources but also perpetuated socio-economic inequalities, especially in employment and education. Van Dijk concluded that addressing digital access without improving digital literacy and community engagement would limit the potential of digital technologies to empower marginalized groups. The study emphasized that digital inclusion strategies must address both physical access to technology and the skills required to use it effectively (Van Dijk, 2017).

While these studies provide valuable insights into the relationship between digital inclusion and youth socio-economic empowerment, several gaps remain. Many of the studies focus primarily on the role of digital literacy and access to technology but do not fully explore the broader socio-economic barriers that rural youth face, such as gender disparities and cultural attitudes toward digital technology. Additionally, there is a lack of longitudinal studies that examine the long-

term impact of digital inclusion on youth empowerment, particularly in rural areas where infrastructure is a significant challenge. The role of community networks and social capital in supporting digital inclusion programs is often overlooked, despite evidence suggesting that strong community ties can enhance the effectiveness of such programs. While these studies examine digital access and skills development, few address the intersection of digital inclusion with broader socio-economic development frameworks, such as local economic policies and labor market dynamics. These gaps suggest the need for a more integrated approach that considers both structural barriers and individual empowerment factors in digital inclusion initiatives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study adopted convergentmixed-methods research design, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches to comprehensively examine the impact of digital inclusion strategies on youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. The rationale for selecting a mixed-methods approach was to capture both descriptive insights and statistical evidence, allowing for a deeper understanding of how digital tools influence youth education, employment, and economic engagement. The integration of these approaches was aimed at triangulating the data, thus providing a more complete and nuanced perspective on the research problem (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). The quantitative component of the study employed a structured Likert-scale questionnaire to gather data from a sample of 292 youth aged 18-34 years in Areka. The questionnaire focused on assessing participants' perceptions of digital inclusion, including their access to digital tools, their level of digital literacy, and the impact of these factors on their socio-economic opportunities. The use of a Likert-scale instrument was appropriate for this study as it allowed respondents to express their level of agreement or disagreement with various statements related to their digital experiences. This approach produced quantifiable data, which could then be statistically analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and relationships between digital inclusion factors and socio-economic empowerment. The Likert-scale method provided a clear, reliable means to

measure youth access to digital resources, their engagement with digital platforms, and the impact these factors have on their economic and educational outcomes (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2020).

The mixed-methods approach used in this study thus enabled the integration of statistical rigor with in-depth qualitative insights, ensuring a more holistic view of the impact of digital inclusion on youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka. This design was crucial for addressing the research problem from multiple angles, ensuring both breadth and depth in the analysis and ultimately contributing to a more complete understanding of how digital tools can support the socio-economic development of youth in rural Ethiopia.

Study Area

This study took place in Areka town and four kebeles (local communities) in the Wolaita zone, located in southern Ethiopia. Areka is a city in southern Ethiopia. Located in some 300 km southwest of the capital, Addis Ababa. This town has a latitude and longitude of 7°4'N 37°42'E and an elevation of 1774 meters above sea level (Borku, Utallo, & Tora, 2024). It is the administrative center of Boloso Sore woreda. At the first stage, Areka town was selected because of the Youth groups are highly dominant Kebeles of the area of the Wolaita. The total population of the town is 62,252. Among those, 31,748 are females and 30,504 are males. The estimated numbers of youths are about 20,282 (Teferi, Samuel, & Markos, 2022). Youth unemployment is a major issue in Areka Town. Despite government and private sector efforts, including microfinance, many young people, even those with education, remain jobless. This problem is exacerbated by a lack of skills and high population growth (Zone, 2020).

Sample Size

According to (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Divakar, 2021) and (Chanuan, Kajohnsak, & Nittaya, 2021), we will use Taro Yamane Formula (Yamane, 1973) for sample size of this study.

Sampling Techniques

A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure that the sample accurately represented the

various attributes of the research population in Wolaita Zone, particularly in the four Kebeles of Areka. This method accurately reflected the population's diversity, producing results that were both precise and dependable. Stratified random sampling involved dividing the population into distinct subgroups (strata) that differed from one another, while individuals within each subgroup exhibited similar characteristics. This approach guaranteed that every subgroup was adequately represented in the sample, enhancing the accuracy and generalizability of the results.

Data Collection Instruments

This study adopted a mixed-methods design, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection instruments to comprehensively examine the impact of digital inclusion strategies on youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka, Wolaita Zone, Ethiopia. The quantitative component primarily used a Likert-scale questionnaire to measure youth's perceptions of digital tools, digital literacy, and their socio-economic outcomes. The questionnaire was administered to 292 youth participants, ensuring that the sample reflected key demographic characteristics, including age, gender, and socio-economic status (Bennett, Johnson, & Liu, 2021). The Likert-scale format allowed for a standardized measurement of participants' agreement with statements related to digital inclusion and its perceived benefits. This instrument underwent a pre-test to ensure clarity and relevance, with adjustments made based on feedback during the pilot phase (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018).

For the qualitative component, interviews were conducted with 50 purposively selected youth participants. These interviews provided deeper insights into the participants' personal experiences with digital literacy programs and their views on how these programs impacted their socio-economic opportunities (Freire, 2020). The semi-structured format allowed for flexibility in probing deeper into specific topics, while maintaining focus on key themes related to digital inclusion and empowerment. Additionally, focus group discussions (FGDs) were held with 50 youth to gather collective perspectives on digital inclusion strategies. FGDs provided richer data on group dynamics and shared experiences, offering a broader understanding

of how digital tools affected youth in a community setting (Elgar et al., 2024).

The study also incorporated secondary data from government reports, NGO publications, and relevant academic sources to contextualize the findings. These secondary sources provided insight into national and regional policies, as well as the challenges and opportunities of digital inclusion in Ethiopia (UNDP, 2022). By combining primary and secondary data, the study offered a comprehensive analysis, integrating both statistical evidence and personal experiences, to provide a full understanding of how digital inclusion strategies affected youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka. This approach ensured triangulation, enhancing the reliability and depth of the research findings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

Data Analysis Procedures

This study employed data analysis procedures that integrated both quantitative and qualitative methods to gain a thorough understanding of the research problem. This mixed-methods approach ensured that the collected data were analyzed in a way that facilitated the integration of numerical data with narrative insights, offering a comprehensive perspective on the findings.

The study analyzed data using quantitative statistical analysis and qualitative thematic analysis methodologies. This ensured that the findings were reliable and fully explained how digital inclusion initiatives affected youth socio-economic empowerment in the study area. The study integrated data from diverse sources and approaches to provide extensive and practical insights to guide digital inclusion and youth empowerment policy and practice. The collection of quantitative data mostly included the use of structured questionnaires. The analysis of quantitative data required the use of statistical software called

When data was collected through semi-structured interviews and focus groups, thematic analysis was

used to make themes and patterns within qualitative data clear. The qualitative data analysis tool and software used was NVivo15, which was stable and multifunctional in terms of data arrangement and categorizations. The platform supported text mining, scripting, graphing, and automated data visualization. Thematic analysis was the qualitative data analysis approach that sought to find, understand, and describe themes within data. This method was applied in qualitative research and could be used with any issue.

Ethical Consideration

In conducting this study, various ethical considerations were carefully adhered to in order to ensure the integrity of the research process and the protection of participants' rights. Ethical standards guided the study in areas such as informed consent, confidentiality, data accuracy, and minimizing harm. According to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education (MoSHE) in Ethiopia, which is responsible for supervising research activities and granting permits, all research had to follow national research strategies and ethical guidelines. To comply with these requirements, a formal request for authorization was submitted to the local MoSHE office in Areka municipal government. Once permission was granted, the study proceeded, and all potential participants were contacted and fully informed about the research purpose, scope, and their rights (Asiva & Rachmayani, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Access to Digital Devices

Access to digital devices plays a significant role in determining how well youth can engage with the digital economy. The dataset shows that smartphones are the most commonly used digital device, followed by tablets and laptops. The following table presents the descriptive statistics of access to digital devices, including smartphones, tablets, and laptops.

Table 4.1: Access to Digital Devices

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	25th Percentile	50th Percentile (Median)	75th Percentile	Max
Access to Smartphone	292	3.31	1.41	1	3	4	4	5
Access to Tablet	292	1.93	1.39	1	1	2	3	5
Access to Laptop/Desktop	292	2.25	1.48	1	1	1.5	3	5

From the table, it is evident that smartphones are the most accessible devices, with an average score of 3.31, indicating that most respondents use smartphones regularly. Smartphones are key tools for accessing social media, online education, and job platforms, which are essential for youth empowerment. However, tablets (mean of 1.93) and laptops (mean of 2.25) are less accessible, with many youth lacking the resources to engage in more complex digital activities, such as online courses or digital business operations.

The limited access to laptops and tablets suggests that many youth in Areka cannot fully engage with digital education and employment opportunities that require more advanced tools. This is a critical issue, as laptops and desktops are necessary for tasks such as video conferencing, large-scale online learning, and managing online businesses, which are key to socio-economic growth.

‘We use phones for social media, but when it comes to government services, the process is complicated and consumes a lot of data.’ (FGD-3 participant-Areka 03).

Many youths in Areka have access to smartphones, as reflected in the mean score of 3.31 for smartphone access. However, the accessibility of more advanced devices like tablets and laptops is more limited. In an interview, one participant noted,

‘Smartphones are okay for basic tasks, but I find it difficult to do more complex work like video editing or attending online classes. Tablets and laptops would help, but they are just too expensive.’ (Female, 22, Areka 02).

Internet Connectivity

Internet connectivity is another crucial factor that impacts how well youth can engage with digital tools and platforms. The quality and accessibility of internet services determine the extent to which youth can access online education, job opportunities, and digital platforms for entrepreneurship. The dataset provides insights into the frequency of internet access, the modes of internet access used by youth, and the overall quality of internet connectivity. The following table presents the descriptive statistics for internet connectivity

Table 4.2: Internet Connectivity

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	25th Percentile	50th Percentile (Median)	75th Percentile	Max
Access to the Internet	292	2.96	1.19	1	2	3	4	5

Mode of Internet Access (Mobile data 3G/4G/5G)	292	3.43	1.29	1	3	4	4	5
Mode of Internet Access (Broadband fiber or DSL)	292	2.03	1.37	1	1	1	3	5
Mode of Internet Access (Public Wi-Fi)	292	3.08	1.45	1	2	3	4	5
Quality of Internet Access	292	2.90	1.20	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency of Internet Use	292	3.18	1.37	1	2	3	4	5

The mean score for internet access is 2.96, indicating that internet access is somewhat accessible, but not universally reliable. The 75th percentile at 4 reflects that a significant portion of respondent’s experience good internet access, yet a notable percentage of youth still face limitations.

Mobile data (3G/4G/5G) is the most common form of internet access, with a mean score of 3.43. This highlights that many youth rely on mobile data to access the internet. However, mobile data is often costly and unreliable, especially in rural areas where network coverage can be weak (Alam & Farhana, 2021). The limited availability of broadband (mean of 2.03) further exacerbates these issues, as broadband typically provides more reliable and faster internet access. Public Wi-Fi, though somewhat accessible (mean of 3.08), is often inconsistent and may not meet the needs of youth engaging in tasks that require high-speed internet.

The quality of internet access is rated moderately (mean of 2.90), with many respondents experiencing poor or unreliable connections. This is a major issue, particularly for those involved in online education or remote work. Poor quality internet limits access to educational resources, job opportunities, and online platforms for entrepreneurship (Robinson et al., 2023). Finally, frequency of internet use has a mean score of 3.18, which shows that most youth use the internet regularly, but not necessarily on a daily basis. The data suggests that internet access is crucial for youth, but

the irregularity of use due to quality or cost factors might hinder consistent engagement with digital tools.

Barriers to Access

Several barriers hinder youth access to digital tools and the internet. These include the high costs of digital devices and internet services, the limited availability of reliable internet connections, and socio-cultural factors that limit digital engagement.

The affordability of devices has a mean score of 2.74, indicating that while some youth find devices somewhat affordable, others struggle to access necessary tools. The high costs of smartphones, laptops, and tablets limit the ability of youth to engage with digital platforms for education, work, or business. Furthermore, the cost of internet services is a major barrier, as youth are often required to allocate a significant portion of their income to stay connected. This financial strain leaves youth with fewer resources for other needs, such as education or healthcare (Schwab et al., 2022).

The lack of broadband access and poor internet quality are significant barriers to digital inclusion. As previously noted, broadband access is limited in Areka, and many youth experience poor internet service, which affects their ability to participate in online learning and professional development opportunities. This issue is particularly evident in rural and semi-urban areas where infrastructure is underdeveloped (Tadesse et al., 2020).

Another key barrier is the lack of digital literacy. Despite having access to smartphones and mobile data, many youth lack the skills to use these tools effectively for education, employment, and entrepreneurship. Digital literacy programs are crucial to bridge this gap and enable youth to use technology to its full potential (O'Donnell & Lim, 2023).

Socio-cultural factors, including cultural restrictions and social norms, can also limit youth's engagement with digital tools. In some cases, traditional attitudes towards technology may discourage youth, especially women, from using digital tools for education or business. These social norms restrict opportunities for marginalized groups to participate in the digital economy (UNICEF, 2020).

The analysis of digital access and infrastructure reveals that while digital tools are becoming more accessible to youth in Areka, significant barriers remain. Smartphones are the most commonly used devices, but access to more advanced tools like laptops and tablets is limited. Internet connectivity, though somewhat accessible, remains unreliable, with mobile data being the primary mode of access. The affordability of devices and internet services continues to be a major issue, further limiting full participation in the digital economy.

The findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to improve digital access and reduce the barriers to technology adoption. Investment in broadband infrastructure, the provision of affordable devices, and digital literacy programs are essential for ensuring that all youth, regardless of their socio-economic background, can participate in digital education, employment, and entrepreneurship opportunities.

Role of Government and NGOs in Digital Inclusion

Government initiatives and the contributions of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a pivotal role in promoting digital inclusion, especially in rural and semi-urban areas where access to digital tools, infrastructure, and training is limited. In Areka, Wolaita Zone, government policies and NGO programs have been key in providing youth with the digital literacy skills necessary for socio-economic empowerment. This section explores the involvement of the government and NGOs in facilitating digital inclusion, including the policies and programs

introduced by the government, the role of NGOs in providing training, and the accessibility of these programs.

Barriers to Digital Inclusion and Youth Empowerment Infrastructure Gaps

Infrastructure gaps are one of the most significant barriers to digital inclusion, as they directly affect access to reliable internet services and digital devices. The dataset highlights two critical issues: the high cost of digital devices and internet access, and the limited availability of digital infrastructure.

The data analysis revealed several infrastructure-related barriers to digital inclusion, which significantly impact youth's ability to engage with digital tools and platforms in Areka, Wolaita Zone. The high cost of digital devices was one of the most significant barriers, with a mean score of 3.75. This score indicates that most respondents perceive the cost of devices such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops as a major obstacle to accessing digital technologies. The 25th percentile score of 5 suggests that a substantial portion of youth find these devices unaffordable, which prevents them from acquiring the necessary tools for education, employment, and entrepreneurship. This financial burden is particularly heavy for youth from low-income backgrounds, who are unable to invest in digital devices essential for participating in the digital economy. The high cost of digital devices, therefore, represents a significant barrier to digital inclusion, particularly in economically disadvantaged communities (Schwab et al., 2022).

Similarly, the high cost of internet access emerged as another significant barrier, with a mean score of 4.00. This score reflects that many youth face challenges affording internet services, which are essential for accessing educational resources, job portals, and online platforms. The 75th percentile score of 5 further indicates that a considerable portion of youth is spending a significant portion of their income on internet and data services. This high cost restricts access to essential digital resources, hindering youth's ability to participate in online learning, employment, and business opportunities. Moreover, the cost of internet services exacerbates the divide between youth who can afford these resources and those who cannot, deepening the inequalities in digital access (Alam & Farhana, 2021).

The data also highlighted the issue of limited internet connectivity, with a mean score of 3.32. This suggests that many youth face difficulties accessing reliable and fast internet connections. While some respondents reported good connectivity, a significant number, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas, experienced poor or intermittent internet access. This lack of stable connectivity hinders their ability to engage effectively with digital platforms, making it difficult to access

online education, employment, or other services. The limited availability of broadband is a major obstacle in these areas, as broadband provides faster and more reliable internet, which is essential for educational and professional activities. Without consistent access to high-quality internet, youth in Areka are unable to fully benefit from the opportunities provided by the digital economy (Tadesse et al., 2020).

Table 4.3: Infrastructure Gaps

Barrier	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	25th Percentile	50th Percentile (Median)	75th Percentile	Max
High Cost of Devices	292	3.75	1.43	1	3	4	5	5
High Cost of Internet/Data	292	4.00	1.26	1	3	5	5	5
Limited Internet Connectivity	292	3.32	1.51	1	2	3	5	5
Poor Digital Infrastructure	292	3.63	1.40	1	3	4	5	5

The infrastructure gaps identified in the dataset clearly hinder the digital engagement of youth in Areka. While smartphones and internet access are common, the high costs of devices and internet services create a barrier for many youth. The lack of sufficient broadband connectivity and advanced digital infrastructure limits the ability of youth to access online educational resources, participate in remote work, or engage in digital entrepreneurship. Addressing these infrastructure gaps is essential to improving digital access and ensuring that all youth, regardless of socio-economic background, can participate in the digital economy (Miller et al., 2022). Cultural and Social Barriers

Cultural and social factors also play a significant role in shaping youth participation in digital programs. Socio-cultural norms, gender roles, and societal expectations can either encourage or discourage youth from engaging with digital tools. The dataset reveals several key cultural and social barriers that limit the ability of youth to fully engage in the digital economy. The data analysis revealed that cultural or social restrictions represent a significant barrier to digital inclusion for some youth in Areka, Wolaita Zone. The mean score for cultural or social restrictions was 2.77, suggesting that while some youth face challenges due to cultural norms, a substantial portion did not perceive

these barriers as limiting. These restrictions are particularly pronounced in rural and traditional communities, where cultural norms can restrict access to digital tools, especially for women. In some instances, traditional beliefs discourage young women from using technology for education or business purposes, thus limiting their opportunities for socio-economic advancement (UNICEF, 2020). The data indicated that these barriers were less common in urban areas, where societal norms are generally more liberal and digital engagement is more widely accepted. This points to the need for targeted interventions that address these cultural barriers, especially in rural areas, to ensure that all youth, regardless of gender or cultural background, have the opportunity to engage with digital technologies.

‘My brother gets the phone more than me. They say girls don’t need to spend time online. Sometimes the content is in English, and it’s hard for me to understand and engage with it. I often wish the materials were available in Amharic or Wolaita language, it would make it much easier for me to understand.’ (FGD-3, young woman-Areka 02).

Structural and socio-cultural barriers continue to prevent inclusive digital access, particularly for rural and female youth.

In addition to cultural barriers, language and literacy barriers were also identified as significant challenges. The mean score for language and literacy barriers was 3.21, indicating that many youth in Areka face challenges related to language when accessing digital content. However, this barrier was less pronounced than cultural restrictions. The primary issue lies in the lack of content in local languages, which limits the ability of youth to engage fully with digital platforms. For youth in Areka, who predominantly speak local languages, access to educational and professional

content in a language they understand is crucial for effective digital engagement. Without localized content, youth are unable to leverage digital tools to their full potential for educational, professional, and entrepreneurial purposes (Fuchs et al., 2020). Addressing language barriers by developing digital content in local languages and enhancing digital literacy programs that cater to these needs will be essential for improving the inclusivity of digital platforms in the region.

Table 4.4: Cultural and Social Barriers

Cultural/Social Barrier	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	25th Percentile	50th Percentile (Median)	75th Percentile	Max
Cultural or Social Restrictions	292	2.77	1.34	1	2	3	4	5
Language and Literacy Barriers	292	3.21	1.47	1	2	3	4	5

Cultural and social barriers significantly limit the digital engagement of youth in Areka, particularly for women and marginalized groups. The moderate score for language and literacy barriers indicates that while local languages are a barrier, they do not entirely prevent digital engagement. The real issue is the availability of digital content in these languages, which is crucial for improving access to education and employment resources. Addressing these barriers requires a focus on culturally sensitive digital content and the inclusion of local languages in digital platforms (Robinson et al., 2023).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Digital Access and Infrastructure

The outcomes of the investigation indicated that Areka had a significant deficiency in both the availability of digital access and the infrastructure around it. The availability of more contemporary devices such as tablets and laptops is still limited, despite the fact that smartphones are the most often used devices for accessing the internet (with a mean score of 3.31). Tablets and laptops, on the other hand, have mean scores of 1.93 and 2.25, respectively. Furthermore, the study found that mobile data is the most frequent means of accessing the internet (with a mean score of 3.43), but the availability of broadband internet is limited (with a mean score of 2.03). This was

determined by the research. The high cost of digital gadgets and internet services has been identified as one of the most significant constraints, according to the findings of the investigation. There is a significant proportion of young individuals who devote a sizeable portion of their money to the acquisition of these services. It is difficult for young people to fully engage in the digital economy due to the gaps in internet access and infrastructure that exist. This is particularly true in areas such as online education and entrepreneurship.

These findings highlight the need of making large expenditures in the expansion of digital infrastructure, particularly broadband access, in places that are currently underserved. This is necessary in order to secure the long-term profitability of the project. For the purpose of making digital devices and internet services more accessible to young people with lower incomes, one of the key objectives of government initiatives should be to reduce the pricing of these items. The investigation of public-private partnerships is something that is encouraged to be done in order to find solutions to the problems that are linked with expenses. Digital access will guarantee that access to technology does not continue to be a luxury reserved for a small segment of the population, but rather that it becomes an opportunity that is available to all individuals.

Recommendations

Aligned with the objectives of this study, the following recommendations are made to enhance digital inclusion and promote socio-economic empowerment for youth in Areka, Wolaita Zone:

1. Objective i: To examine the relationship between digital inclusion strategies and youth socio-economic empowerment in Areka, Wolaita Zone

Develop community-based programs to address gender and cultural barriers that hinder youth, particularly young women, from fully engaging with digital tools for education, business, and social purposes. Promoting gender equality and raising awareness about digital opportunities can help bridge these barriers and empower youth socio-economically.

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